

OPPOSITE-GENDER PATIENT EXAMINATION IN CLINICAL PRACTICE: A CROSS-SECTIONAL ANALYSIS OF RADIOLOGISTS ATTITUDES, PRACTICES, AND PATIENT COMFORT

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Abstract

Objectives: This study aimed to investigate the influence of cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, identify key cultural or religious concerns leading to discomfort or refusal, and evaluate the availability and effectiveness of institutional support mechanism (policies, training, and chaperone protocols) and radiologists' preparedness to deal with cultural sensitivities in opposite-gender ultrasound examinations.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from December 2024 to April 2025 in six government hospitals located in Wah Cantt, Pakistan. A convenience sample of 200 radiology residents and practitioners completed a validated questionnaire adapted from the cross-cultural competence continuum was used. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics 25, employing descriptive statistics, chi-square tests ($p < 0.05$).

Result: Majority of participants reported cultural impacts on patient interactions, with a significant association between perceived impact of cultural or gender norm on patient comfort levels. Notably, 21.3% of those perceiving cultural impact reported slight discomfort, compared to 5% without discomfort, while 20% and 16.3% noted moderate and great discomfort, respectively. Personal modesty (30.0%) and religious reasons (28.7%) were primary concerns for patient discomfort or refusal. Institutional policy availability was significantly associated with radiologists' preparedness ($p=0.001$), unlike cultural sensitivity training ($p=0.008$) or chaperone protocols ($p=0.163$).

Conclusion: Cultural beliefs and gender norms notably influence patient comfort in opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, driven by modesty and religious concerns. Inconsistent institutional support underscores the need for

INTRODUCTION

Patient comfort, defined as the subjective sense of ease, security, and psychological well-being experienced during medical procedures, is significantly shaped by interpersonal interactions and cultural contexts.⁽¹⁾ In ultrasound examinations, which often involve physical proximity and exposure of sensitive body areas, patient comfort is crucial for fostering trust and improving diagnostic outcomes, particularly in opposite-gender settings. Cultural beliefs and societal gender norms can influence patients' perceptions of modesty and privacy, impacting their willingness to undergo such procedures. This study, conducted in government hospitals in Wah Cantt, Pakistan, explores how these cultural factors affect patient comfort from the perspectives of radiology residents and practitioners, aiming to enhance patient-centered care in diverse clinical settings.⁽²⁾ Patient discomfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations is a notable concern in radiology, with 20–40% of patients reporting unease, especially in procedures involving pelvic or obstetric ultrasounds.⁽³⁾ Cultural and religious values often drive this discomfort, manifesting as concerns about physical contact with an opposite-gender practitioner, compounded by inadequate communication or lack of chaperone options. These issues are further influenced by varying levels of cultural competence among radiology professionals, which may differ between residents and experienced practitioners due to differences in training and exposure, as observed in recent South Asian studies on healthcare cultural dynamics.⁽⁴⁾ Current literature provides insights into patient-provider dynamics in medical imaging, though specific exploration of cultural influences in opposite-gender ultrasound examinations is limited. Previous studies highlight gender disparities in ultrasound-guided procedural participation among radiology trainees, suggesting potential impacts on their cultural competence in patient interactions.⁽⁵⁾ Similarly, studies also identify variability in point-of-care ultrasound competency among Jordanian radiologists, emphasizing the need

for standardized training to address cultural and clinical challenges.⁽⁶⁾ Other studies, such as those on communication barriers in multicultural radiography settings or patient understanding of ultrasound procedures, underscore the importance of cultural competence and clear communication but do not specifically address opposite-gender dynamics in ultrasound examinations, highlighting a critical area for further research. A significant research gap exists in understanding how cultural factors shape patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, particularly from the perspectives of both radiology residents and practitioners.⁽⁷⁾ While studies have explored general patient-provider interactions or gender preferences in primary care, the unique dynamics of ultrasound procedures, which require close physical contact, remain underexplored. This gap is particularly pronounced in culturally diverse settings like Pakistan, where religious and societal norms strongly influence patient preferences. The lack of research on institutional policies and training addressing these cultural sensitivities limits the development of practices that enhance patient trust and comfort in radiology settings.⁽⁸⁾ This study aims to investigate the influence of cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations by assessing the perceptions of radiology residents and practitioners in government hospitals in Wah Cantt, Pakistan, from December 2024 to April 2025. It seeks to identify key cultural or religious concerns leading to patient discomfort or refusal and evaluate the effectiveness of institutional policies, training, and chaperone protocols. The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform targeted interventions that enhance patient trust and satisfaction, addressing a critical gap in culturally sensitive radiology practices.⁽⁹⁾ By providing insights into cultural barriers and institutional measures, the study aims to contribute to equitable healthcare delivery and inform global radiology training frameworks.⁽¹⁰⁾

- To assess the perceived impact of cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations
- To identify the most commonly reported cultural or religious concerns that lead to patient discomfort or refusal for opposite-gender ultrasound examinations
- To evaluate the availability and effectiveness of institutional support factors (policies, training, and chaperone protocols) in addressing radiologists preparedness to deal with cultural sensitivities during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional study was conducted from December 2024 to April 2025 in six government hospitals such as P.O.F Hospital, Izzat Ali Shah Hospital, City Hospital, Wah General Hospital, Umer Hospital and Noori Hospital Pakistan. These tertiary care facilities were selected due to their diverse patient populations and high volume of ultrasound examinations, providing a suitable context to explore cultural influences on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound procedures. The study targeted radiology departments to capture insights from both radiology residents and practitioners, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of cultural dynamics in clinical practice within a culturally diverse region known for its strong religious and societal gender norms. A convenience sample of 200 radiology residents and practitioners was recruited from the radiology departments of the selected government hospitals. The sample included both male and female participants to reflect diverse perspectives on opposite-gender patient interactions. Residents were in various stages of their training, while practitioners had at least two years of post-residency experience, allowing for a comparison of cultural competence and approaches to patient care across different levels of expertise. The sample size of 200 participants was determined using a power calculation based on prior radiology and cultural competence studies. Assuming a 30% prevalence of reported cultural impacts on patient comfort (based on preliminary data), a 95% confidence level, and a

10% margin of error, a minimum sample of 73 was required. We recruited 200 participants to account for potential non-response, ensuring sufficient power (80%) to detect significant differences in perceptions and practices between residents and practitioners. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire adapted from the cross-cultural competence continuum, tailored to assess the perceived impact of cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations. Key questionnaire items included: (1) a 5-point Likert scale assessing the perceived impact of cultural beliefs on patient interactions (1 = no impact, 5 = severe impact), (2) multiple-choice questions identifying specific reasons for patient discomfort or refusal (e.g., personal modesty, religious reasons, family influence), and (3) categorical questions evaluating the availability of chaperone protocols (e.g., always provided, encouraged but not mandatory) and cultural sensitivity training (e.g., comprehensive, minimal, none). Participants completed the questionnaire anonymously in either paper-based or electronic formats during scheduled departmental meetings to maximize response rates. The data collection process ensured confidentiality and compliance with ethical standards, with approval obtained from the institutional review boards of the participating hospitals. Inclusion criteria encompassed radiology residents and practitioners actively involved in performing ultrasound examinations in the selected hospitals, willing to provide informed consent. Exclusion criteria included non-radiology medical staff, participants not engaged in direct patient care, and those unwilling to participate. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize demographic characteristics and questionnaire responses. Chi-square was used to identify cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. The analysis aimed to provide robust insights into cultural barriers and the effectiveness of institutional measures in addressing them.

RESULTS:

This cross-sectional study analyzed responses from 200 radiology residents and practitioners in government hospitals in Wah Cantt, Pakistan, from

December 2024 to April 2025 using IBM SPSS Statistics 25. Data were collected via a validated questionnaire adapted from the cross-cultural competence continuum, with analysis employing descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, logistic regression, and frequency distributions. Key findings included 76.3% (n=61) of participants reporting

cultural impacts on patient interactions, with female radiologists showing 68.4% lower odds of reporting cultural impact compared to male radiologists (OR = 0.316, p=0.032). Additionally, a significant association was found between experience and training effectiveness (p=0.042).

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Radiology Residents and Practitioners (n=200)

Characteristic	Category	F (%)
Age Category	20–25 years	18 (9.0%)
	26–30 years	102 (51.0%)
	31–35 years	60 (30.0%)
	36–40 years	20 (10.0%)
Sex Distribution	Male	70 (35.0%)
	Female	130 (65.0%)
Professional Experience	1–3 years	70 (35.0%)
	4–7 years	90 (45.0%)
	8–10 years	40 (20.0%)

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the 200 radiology practitioners participated in the study. The majority of respondents were aged between 26 and 30 years (51.0%), followed by those aged 31–35 years (30.0%), while smaller proportions fell into the 20–25 years (9%) and 36–40 years (10.0%) age groups. In terms of gender distribution, 65.0% of participants were female (n = 130), and 35.0% were male (n = 70).

As for professional experience, the highest proportion of respondents had 4–7 years of work experience (45.0%), followed by 1–3 years (35.0%) and 8–10 years (20.0%). These demographics indicate that the sample primarily consisted of young to mid-career professionals, with a female-majority representation and substantial experience in clinical radiology practice.

Table 2

Association Between Sociocultural Influence and Patient Experience Levels in Gender-Discordant Ultrasound Interactions (n = 200)

Patient Experience Level	Perceived Sociocultural Influence		χ^2 (4)	p-value
	Present (Yes)	Absent (No)		
No discomfort	20 (10.0%)	20 (10.0%)	30.062	0.01
Mild discomfort	43 (21.5%)	10 (5.0%)		
Moderate discomfort	40 (20.0%)	8 (4.0%)		
High discomfort	33 (16.5%)	0 (0.0%)		
Very high discomfort	17 (8.5%)	9 (4.5%)		

The table 2 highlights a significant association between perceived cultural impact on patient comfort levels, as determined by a chi-square test $\chi^2(4) =$

30.062, p = 0.01). Among patients reporting no discomfort, 20(10%) felt "not at all" comfortable, mirroring the 20 (10%) with cultural impact in the

same category, whereas 43(21.5%) with cultural impact reported mild discomfort compared to only 10 (5%) without. The trend continues with 40 (20%) and 8 (4.0%) of those perceiving cultural impact reporting moderate and great discomfort respectively, with no patients in the "to a great extent" category reporting

no impact, and only 9 (4.5%) in the "to a very great extent" category indicating no impact. These results suggest that a perceived cultural or gender norm impact is significantly linked to heightened discomfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations.

Table 3

Cultural and Religious Concerns Leading to Patient Discomfort or Refusal (n=200)

Reason	F%
Cultural Beliefs	15(7.5%)
Religious reasons	57(28.7%)
Personal modesty	60(30.0%)
Family influence	43(21.3%)
No clear reason provided	25(12.5%)

Table-3 identifies the most reported cultural or religious concerns contributing to patient discomfort or refusal of opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, participants were asked to indicate observed reasons provided by patients. The most frequently cited factor was personal modesty, reported by 60 respondents (30.0%), followed closely by religious reasons, reported by 57 respondents (28.5%). Family influence was mentioned by 43

participants (21.5%), while cultural beliefs were noted less frequently, with only 15 respondents (7.5%) reporting it as a reason. Additionally, 25 respondents (12.5%) stated that no clear reason was provided by patients. These findings suggest that individual values, particularly modesty and religious considerations, are the primary drivers of patient discomfort or refusal in opposite-gender imaging scenarios.

Table 4

Availability and Effectiveness of Institutional Support Factors and Radiologist Preparedness(n=200)

Institutional Support Factors		Radiologists Preparedness		χ^2 (1)	p-value
		Yes	No		
Formalized Clinical Governance Policies	Available	98	25	25.168	0.001
	Not Available	35	42		
Structured Cultural Competency Interventions	Present	88	45	0.008	0.928
	Absent	45	22		
Supervised Examination Safeguards	Present	105	48	1.945	0.163
	Absent	28	19		

Table 4 shows Chi-square test was conducted to examine the relationship between institutional support mechanisms and radiologists perceived preparedness for handling cultural sensitivities during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations. The availability of institutional policies showed a statistically significant association with preparedness,

χ^2 (1) = 25.168, p = 0.001, indicating that radiologists working in institutions with formal policies were more likely to feel adequately prepared. In contrast, no significant associations were found between preparedness and either the presence of cultural sensitivity training χ^2 (1) = 0.008, p = 0.928 or chaperone protocols χ^2 (1) = 1.945, p = 0.163). These

findings suggest that institutional policies may play a more critical role in practitioner readiness than training or chaperone guidelines alone.

Discussion:

The findings of this study underscore the impact of cultural beliefs and gender norms on patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, aligning with the first objective.⁽¹¹⁾ The results from Table 2 reveal a significant association between perceived cultural or gender norm impact and patient comfort levels during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations, with a chi-square test indicating statistical significance. Notably, 21.3% of patients perceiving cultural impact reported slight discomfort compared to only 5% of those without, while 20% and 16.3% of those acknowledging cultural influence felt moderate and great discomfort, respectively, with no patients in the "to a great extent" category reporting no cultural impact. This suggests that cultural and gender norms markedly heighten discomfort, aligning with findings that cultural beliefs shape patient interactions in radiology settings.⁽¹²⁾ It shows such patterns may stem from increased practitioner awareness of diverse patient reactions, as experience often amplifies sensitivity to cultural norms.⁽¹³⁾ Additionally, this discomfort echoes observations in Southeast Asian contexts, where gender congruence influences patient preferences, underscoring the need for tailored approaches to mitigate inequalities in care.⁽¹⁴⁾ Addressing the second objective, Table 3 shows personal modesty (30.0%) and religious reasons (28.7%) as key drivers of patient discomfort or refusal in opposite-gender ultrasound exams, followed by family influence (21.3%). This reflects Pakistan's cultural emphasis on modesty and gender segregation, rooted in Islamic values.⁽¹⁵⁾ Similar patterns appear in other regions with comparable cultural norms.⁽¹⁶⁾ Family influence points to social pressures affecting decisions. This echoes findings common in rural communities.⁽¹⁷⁾ Culturally sensitive practices in radiology are thus essential for patient's comfort.⁽¹⁸⁾ For the third objective, Table 4 indicates a significant association between the availability of institutional policies and radiologists perceived preparedness for handling cultural sensitivities during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations. This suggests formal policies enhance readiness to address cultural

discomfort. In contrast, no notable link emerged for cultural sensitivity training or chaperone protocols. This highlights a potential gap in training effectiveness.⁽¹⁹⁾ Chaperone guidelines also appear insufficient alone to boost preparedness.⁽²⁰⁾ Thus, standardized institutional policies seem critical for supporting culturally sensitive care.⁽²¹⁾ While female patient discomfort due to cultural norms is prominent, male patients also report unease in opposite-gender ultrasound exams, particularly in sensitive pelvic or genitourinary procedures. Privacy concerns likely contribute to this discomfort.⁽²²⁾ However, some patients may value expertise over gender in urgent cases, potentially lessening cultural barriers. In Pakistan's conservative context, the preference for same-gender care remains strong, necessitating attention to both male and female concerns for holistic radiology practice. Cultural beliefs and institutional support critically shape radiology practice in diverse regions like Pakistan.⁽²³⁾ The lack of association between cultural sensitivity training and preparedness highlights training limitations. Inconsistent policies further underscore the need for standardized protocols, such as mandatory chaperones, to address cultural barriers effectively. However, personal modesty concerns (30.0%) and religious concerns (28.7%) as key issues, calling for standardized protocols like chaperone availability and tailored communication training.⁽²⁴⁾ Also table 4 reveals gaps in institutional support, with policy availability linked to preparedness suggesting cultural competence be integrated into training.⁽²⁵⁾ Future studies should use qualitative methods to capture patient views, enhancing understanding of cultural influences on ultrasound exams.

Conclusion:

This study in government hospitals in Wah Cantt, Pakistan, underscores that cultural beliefs and gender norms significantly shape patient comfort during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations. The exploration revealed that cultural and religious concerns, particularly those tied to modesty and societal expectations, often lead to patient discomfort or refusal. Additionally, the evaluation of institutional support mechanisms highlighted the critical role of formal policies in preparing radiologists to address cultural sensitivities, while identifying gaps in training

and chaperone protocols. These insights emphasize the need for standardized policies, enhanced cultural competence training, and consistent chaperone availability to foster patient-centered, culturally sensitive care in radiology settings.

Limitation and recommendation:

This research had a few limiting factors that can impact on the external validity of its results. The convenience sample of government hospitals in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan, restricts the representation of the private facilities or rural environments, where the cultural norms and resources may vary. The cross-sectional design further limits the possibility to determine the changes over time or determine causality of the cultural factors the comfort levels. Moreover, the practitioner-centered approach does not include the direct patient voice, which might introduce more insights regarding the personal and cultural factors affecting discomfort in opposite-gender ultrasound exams.

In order to overcome the described cultural factors and institutional voids, radiology departments would be advised to develop uniform policies requiring the presence of a chaperone during opposite-gender ultrasound examinations to promote patient comfort and confidence. It is suggested that more extensive cultural competence training programs be implemented to accommodate the different societal or religious norms in Pakistan so that radiologists would be more adequately prepared in handling patient sensitivities. It is also high time that hospitals focus on improving the female workforce in the radiology department to match the patient preference of same-gender care especially in conservative environments. The next stage of research must include qualitative methodology, including interviewing patients, to fix their first-hand experience and supplement the experience of practitioners. Also, future research should be extended to cover the private and rural facilities to gain more insight into cultural dynamics and shape radiology practice equitable and patient-centered.

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